

SHORT COMMUNICATIONS

On the Negative S_v -Coefficient in Masson's Equation for some Common Electrolytes in Solvents of Large Molecules

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The apparent molal volume, ϕ_v , of electrolytes in solutions is, in general, given by the Masson's equation¹, namely,

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^0 + S_v \sqrt{C},$$

where ϕ_v^0 is the limiting apparent molal volume, C , the concentration in gm. mol. litre⁻¹ and S_v , the slope of the ϕ_v vs $\sqrt{C}$ curve. In aqueous solutions, the slope S_v is positive for common electrolytes as well as for the tetraalkylammonium halides (R_4NX), containing the smaller of the R_4N^+ ions, i.e., Me_4N^+ and Et_4N^+ , but it is negative for the R_4NX salts of the larger R_4N^+ ions at ordinary concentrations^{2,3,4,5} ($C \geq 0.1M$). In 1968 Millero⁶ observed a negative slope (S_v) for $NaNO_3$ and $NaBr$ (also, perhaps, for some other salts as well⁶) in N-methylpropionamide (NMP), and ascribed it to be due to the high dielectric constant of the solvent. Since S_v values, in the same solvent, may be positive or negative, depending on the electrolyte dissolved^{2,3,4,5,7,8}, and for an electrolyte in the same solvent, the sign of S_v may vary with the concentration, the explanation suggested by Millero is not convincing. Some workers have suggested the negative slope for the larger of the R_4NX salts in water to be due to the enhancement of its tetrahedral structure by the hydrophobic R_4N^+ -water interaction^{3,9}. This explanation is again unsatisfactory since the negative slope has been observed in non-aqueous solutions^{6,7,8} as well, in which neither the tetrahedral structure is present nor the lyophobic enforcement of the solvent structure is expected¹⁰.

In order to explain the behaviour of the larger R_4N -iodides in aqueous and non-aqueous solutions^{5,7,8}, it has been suggested^{5,7,8} that the negative slope would occur if the volume of the solute ions is relatively large as compared to that of the solvent molecule and if the interpenetration of the ions takes place¹¹.

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11. Ionic interpenetration is possible only in the R_4N^+ ions but not in the common compact ions.

The larger of the R_4N^+ ions would be quite voluminous in comparison to the solvent molecules which could be accommodated inside the voids formed by the R_4N^+ ions when they come in contact at appropriate concentrations; besides, the inter-penetration of the R_4N^+ ions would occur at higher concentrations and so the negative slope in such cases can be easily explained.

A corollary of this concept is that, if the solute ions are sufficiently small as compared to the solvent molecules, negative S_v values should be observed, because the solute ions would be accommodated in the voids formed by the solvent molecules; the strong ion-solvent interaction in such cases, would lead to contraction which would increase with the increase in concentration. The negative slope observed by Millero⁶, for some common electrolytes in NMP, could thus be explained. Our recent studies on the apparent molal volume of common electrolytes in N-methylacetamide (NMA) also yield negative S_v values, even down to 0.02M, for NaCl, NaBr, KNO_3 and KBr etc. Here again, the NMP molecule is large as compared to the ions and the electrostatic ion-solvent interaction is expected to be appreciable and so the negative S_v should be expected. There are, of course, some marked exceptions, e.g., the positive values for LiCl, and KI in NMA, which have to be explained. However, the general results do indicate the important role of the relative volumes of the solvent and the solute particles^{12,13} in determining the sign of the slope of the ϕ_v vs $\sqrt{C}$ curves of different electrolytes in various solvents. The explanation proposed here, appears to give a more easily comprehensible physical picture of the ion-solvent interaction than the vague suggestions advanced previously by other workers^{3,9}. A detailed account of the work underway, in this laboratory, will be communicated later.

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